

Dellingr Phase 2: Deliverable 1

Resource Exchange Models

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1 Executive Summary

The NeIC Dellingr project is investigating how a lightweight framework for sharing High Performance Computing (HPC) resources¹ can be implemented between participating countries.² These resources will be open to eligible researchers³ from the participating countries who wish to access resources in other participating countries. A feature of this resource sharing includes the case where the computing project is performed in an HPC centre outside the home country of the researcher.

This document gives a description of the possibilities and issues related to sharing High Performance computing resources within the participating countries. This document consists of the following sections:

- Purpose of the document – defines the scope of the deliverable and its intended audience;
- Expected benefits of exchanging resources – describes the targeted use cases of the resource sharing framework and means of tracking its performance;
- Resource exchange models – describes proposed resource exchange models and provides brief summary of their analysis;
- Validation with pilot projects – briefly describes the Dellingr resource sharing pilot that showed that resources can be shared;
- Fungibility, exchange rates and metrics – describes the considerations for the cross-border resource accounting;
- Benchmarking the pilot resources – contains description of the approaches taken to compare resources committed to the common pool;
- Cross-border resource marketplace – contains the expected functionality of a one-stop-shop implementing selected resource sharing framework.

2 Purpose of the Document

The purpose of this document is to describe, to NeIC and the national providers of HPC computing e-infrastructure in the participating countries, a HPC resource exchange model. This document describes the motivations for sharing resources as outlined in the project plan [1], the framework to

¹Defined generally as compute, network and storage e-infrastructure.

²Currently this includes the Nordic countries and Estonia.

³At the moment we do not address commercial users that some countries have agreements to provide/use resources.

share resources and the exchange mechanisms. This document is to be used as a basis for further discussions on HPC resource sharing leading to a general agreement. It can also be used to form a basis for a future Dellingr pilot that would deploy a prototype of the proposed resource exchange model, exchange rates and framework.

3 Expected Benefits of Exchanging Resources

National computing centres for academic research are generally funded by ministries responsible for scientific research and higher education – the same ministries that fund universities. The roles of computing centres and universities are distinct: Universities do scientific research and give education. Computing centres help them to reach their goals in these functions. Money allocated to computing centres should provide better, or at least, comparable results as the same amount allocated to universities. Resource exchange can advance scientific research and education in two ways.

First, it can open new research opportunities. Users may have certain technical requirements regarding CPU performance and efficiency, memory size and bus bandwidth, disk storage size and speed, as well as type and speed of interconnects. Other factors users may consider are the type and version of compilers, software and system administration support, and also social and political factors such as available certifications of the system, the source of the electricity and terms of services of a particular resource provider. Users may also prefer one system to another simply based on the perceived ease-of-use, level of user support and other intangibles or subjective measures of an attribute of a particular system. If one centre does not have certain hardware or software that a research group needs, they can ideally use suitable resources made available from other countries.

Second, resource exchange can balance temporary resource shortages, for example during computer procurements. In the time between when a cluster is decommissioned and the new cluster is available, it is good if the users do not need to wait for the newly commissioned system but instead can “borrow” resources from another provider. This long-term pool of shared resources can be used as temporary resources for users.

Third, another sharing scenario to consider is when the HPC resources in one country are constantly “overbooked” and queuing times become unacceptably long for the users, while in some other countries there might be an excess of free resources.

It is up to the respective countries to decide whether to exchange resources or not. The Dellingr project can assist the decision makers of each respective country by providing them with enough facts so that they can make an informed decision.

3.1 Metrics

The HPC resources in each country are made available in order to aid researchers in their work and thus the final output is in the form of publications. Therefore an important metric to measure is the number of **papers published** from work performed on shared resources obtained through this framework. The number of publications is not, however, sufficient as the only metric, because researchers would produce publications even without any resource exchange, and various fields publish at different rates making the number of published papers a measure biased towards publication-heavy research fields. The access to a variety of different resources rather raises the *quality* of the publications than the number of them. Therefore the second important metric is the **perceived benefit** of getting access to the shared resource pool. It is important to know what each research group would have done differently if they were not given access to a particular system. Both the information regarding papers published and the perceived benefit should be collected from users after they have carried out their project.

Also some basic data about the resource-sharing framework complementing the two metrics given above will be collected over time. Examples of such basic data are given below:

- Number of project applications – How attractive and useful researchers find the resource sharing framework?
- Number of participating national providers (countries) – How useful national providers see us?
- Amount of core-hours⁴ are shared in total – The more useful national providers see the framework, the more they will contribute.
- Usage of shared core-hours as a percentage – How well the selection of projects works?
- Time from application to resource access – How easily the framework can respond to temporary resource shortages?

4 Resource Exchange Mechanism

Given that a pool of shared resources exists, a mechanism is needed to facilitate the exchange of resources. The resource exchange mechanism should address how the eligible researchers from the participating countries are assigned to (or allocated) HPC resources which are provided and shared between the participating national providers. The mechanism should be lightweight and transparent so that the overhead of applying and allocating resources to a researcher or group of researchers is minimal.

⁴A core-hour is defined as the usage of a single core of a multi-core processor for one wall-time hour.

4.1 Definitions:

In the description of the resource exchange models the following actors and entities have been identified.

- **User:** A user is the person, researcher, employed at a university in a participating country, who is the Principal Investigator (PI), or project leader, for a research project that requests allocation on any of the available resources.
- **Resource:** A resource is a high performance computer made available by a participating country. A country may make more than one resource available. A resource is allocated to users via the units of measurement: typically “core-hours”.
- **Project application:** A project application is the description of the research a user wants to perform using a resource. The project application contains the names, affiliation, employment position, field of research et.al. of the project members i.e. participating researchers. A user uses a project application to apply for an amount of core-hours.
- **Application deadline:** An application deadline is the last date by which a project application must be supplied to the evaluation committee to be considered for accessing a resource for the project period.
- **Project:** A project is an approved project application, i.e. research being performed and the researchers performing it on a resource as described in a project application submitted by the user.
- **Project period:** The project period is the time period during which a project is granted access to a resource. The time period is usually set to a maximum of 12 months. A project period may overlap the time between several application deadlines.
- **Common web service:** The project application can be facilitated via common web service through which the user submits the Project Application.
- **User Agreement:** The user agreement describes/stipulates the obligations a user has towards the resource provider. The user accepts a national user agreement in order to be able to use the resources made available by the participating national provider.
- **Evaluation committee:** The evaluation committee is a person, or group of persons, who holds technical expertise and who in some way, by the national providers, such as (in the Swedish case) SNIC, is contracted to perform technical evaluation. The evaluation committee, based on the project application, decides if the project application of a user project shall be

granted access to a resource and which resource the user shall be granted access to in order to utilize granted core-hours to perform research via the resource.

- **System operator:** A system operator is a member of staff at the provider, which provides each resource. The system operator is responsible for creating accounts and passwords for project members according to the routines at each resource.

4.2 Models

Five models to exchange resources have been considered and are described below in order of perceived complexity starting with the most regulated one:

1. **Regular calls for applications using a single central evaluation committee:** The evaluation committee would necessarily be composed of members from each of the participating countries similar to the PRACE Tier-0 procedure. The user may request a particular resource, but it is the evaluation committee who decides which resource the users project shall be placed on. The duration of a project will be set by the evaluation committee. A project application must be sent in to the committee by the application deadline. A schematic of the process can be seen in Figure 1

Pros: This model would have the advantage of screening all applications to the shared resources, ensuring a uniformity in the evaluation of the applications. Having a committee screening the applications give the possibility of evaluating the applications from a scientific standpoint.

Cons: Depending on the size limit of the applications there is a risk of large allocations dominating the resources. This model would risk repeating the PRACE Tier-0 procedures for resource sharing. If the applications are small, then the administrative and time overheads for such a procedure would probably be prohibitive for researchers looking for a lightweight method to access resources.

2. **Regular calls for applications with distributed evaluation committees:** In this model the participating national evaluation committees receive applications for their respective resources from the users. The user may request a specific resource with a specific participating member, but it is the national evaluation committees that decide which resource the project shall be using. A national committee may decide that none of the resources of that participating country is to be made available to the project and instead refer the user to a different country and evaluation committee. A schematic of the process can be seen in Figure 2

Figure 1: Regular calls for applications using a single central evaluation committee.

Figure 2: Regular calls for applications with distributed evaluation committees.

Pros: Compared to the model above, there should be less administrative and time overhead. As above, having a committee screening the applications give the possibility of evaluating the applications from a scientific standpoint.

Cons: The selected applications from each national committee would have to be combined to fit into the available resources. There would have to be regular communication between the committees to ensure uniformity in the evaluation of the applications both from a technical and a scientific standpoint. Similar to the model above, this model risks being seen as a repetition of PRACE Tier-1 procedures.

3. **Regular calls for applications without evaluation:** In this model, resources are pledged by each country in time with the calls for applications. The applications are accepted without technical or scientific evaluation provided the applicants meet eligibility and resources are allocated on a first-come first-served basis. The user will send his or her application to the system operator of a particular resource. The system operator will grant access to the resource if the project is eligible to use the resource. A schematic of the process can be seen in Figure 3

Figure 3: Regular calls for applications without evaluation.

Pros: This procedure is more lightweight than the first two apart from verifying the applicants' eligibility, thus lowering the bar for a researcher to consider moving from one resource to another.

Cons: The regularity of the calls and resource pledge creates an artificial time constraint on the process. This model implies that there is a facilitating technical infrastructure present that will provide the system operator with all pertinent data. The model does not fit with current resource sharing policies at least in some countries, in particular Sweden, where all projects must be pre-approved by a (national) board.

4. **Continuous exchange of computing projects between countries** In this case a pool of resources is available across the participating countries and the eligible applicants apply for resources. Applications are evaluated continuously with some countries also allowing automatic provisioning of resources if the application fits the policy. The user will send his or her application to the system operator of a particular resource. The system operator will grant access to the resource if the project is eligible to use the resource. A schematic of the process can be seen in Figure 4

Figure 4: Continuous exchange of computing projects between countries.

Pros: This model makes sense for computing projects that are relatively small and require resources with low time and administrative overheads thereby enabling users to quickly move to a different resource in case their regularly used resource should experience problems. This

model is conceptually the most natural for applicants as it allows potentially the shortest time to resources.

Cons: This model implies that there is a facilitating technical infrastructure present that will provide the system operator with all pertinent data. There is also the risk of under-usage if a resource is not filled to capacity as the unused part of the pledged resource cannot be returned to the pledging country. The model does not fit with current resource sharing policies at least in some countries, in particular Sweden, where all projects must be pre-approved by a (national) board.

- Generic project model** In this case a “generic” project is created within each shared resource with an allocation the size of the contributed number of core-hours. A PI is assigned to each project with the responsibility to add and remove co-investigators to the project. Researchers in participating countries are eligible to be added as co-investigators to the project by the PI to perform their research. The co-investigators will use the resource for their research until their normal resource is again available at which point the PI will remove the user from the list of co-investigators. A schematic of the process can be seen in Figure 5

Figure 5: Generic project managed by local PI’s.

Pros: This model is good for instances where researchers are having unexpected interruption of their service. The lead-time for a researcher to get access to a resource will be very short

and therefore it will be able to respond to temporary unavailability due to upgrades or longer system outages.

Cons: The PI will in this model be tasked to check for the eligibility of the researcher. In this model there is no way of making the co-investigator state what type of research he or she will be doing unless this is done in the account application process. The resource utilization may be low as the entire allocation provided by the center will be assigned to the project.

All of the suggested resource sharing models assumes a general user agreement acceptable by all participating countries. A common difficulty with all of these models will be to address the policy and legal issues of sharing resources across national borders, particularly in agreeing on a common user agreement over the Nordic region. The different participating countries have commented the exchange models below:

- Iceland: The Icelandic resources are “first come, first serve” with some fair-share process to balance the queue between active users. Thus, there is no evaluation committee. Any eligible user is able to run on the cluster. Therefore, methods 1 and 2 are sub-optimal from the Icelandic point-of-view. Method 4 is regarded as slightly better from the Icelandic perspective than 3 as this allows the Icelandic systems to distribute the load throughout the year more evenly.
- Sweden: The application mechanism needs to be lightweight and continuous (i.e. no need to apply by a certain date). However, there must be some review process to any project application. Therefore, the resource exchange mechanism 2 is preferable. The resource exchange mechanism 4 is also acceptable given that some review process is involved for each application. The model selected should also act as an aggregator of project application data to facilitate continuous resource exchange. The infrastructure should interface with the national portals so that the review is performed, and decisions are taken at the national level.
- Estonia: Needs to apply an initial validation process to the organization that will be applying for resources to define usage and accounting policy. After that organization can request and receive resources in automated fashion. People representing organizations must have reasonably strong digital identities to get access to resources. Estonia does accounting of resources in "EUR" with costs being very close to cost of ownership. Different types of resources have different pricing. Model 4 is preferred as it very closely resembles the current process in Estonia.
- Finland: The model 4 is favoured by the Finnish centre. Finland can automatically provision resources for projects approved by other partners, as long as the project does public research and its members are from universities or government research institutes.
- Denmark: Input to be received.

- Norway: Norway participates as an observer in the Dellingr project.

Regardless of which model for resource exchange is chosen, there will be policy and legal issues concerning the exchange of computing resources within the Nordic region. The Dellingr project will have to address those issues but they are independent of which model for resource sharing the Dellingr project see as the most promising one. The Dellingr project has decided to investigate using the fourth model (continuous exchange of computing projects between countries) as the resource exchange mechanism.

5 Validation with Pilot Projects

The Dellingr project has run a small-scale resource sharing pilot that used the fourth resource exchange mechanism as outlined in Section 4. The resources, shown in Table 1, were shared through an open call for applications from researchers throughout the participating countries. The pilot applications that were accepted ranged from 50 to 250 k core hours over a maximum period of time of 9 months (September 2017 to June 2018). The pilot project was used to validate that it is possible for HPC resources to be shared across borders and at the same time respect the requirements for accepting projects of the contributing countries.

The pilot resources were assigned on a “first-come first-served” basis once the requests were verified to come from bone-fide academic applicants. Also, the applications had to be verified that they were qualified to use academic HPC resources in the hosting country. The applications that were rejected were so due to: two coming from a state-funded non-academic research centre; for one application no suitable hardware was available in the shared resources. Of the accepted 18 project applications, 9 requested 200 k-core-hours or more.

This pilot demonstrated that it is possible to share HPC resources across borders on a small scale. The procedures in accepting applications were followed in each hosting country and the users gave generally positive feedback. A more detailed report on this subject is an upcoming deliverable of the Dellingr project.

6 Fungibility, Exchange Rates and Metrics

The resources committed to a shared pool need to be accounted as they have certain value to the national providers that commit the resources. Such accounting should serve as a basis for creating a sustainable model for sharing with clear benefits for parties involved.

6.1 Resource fungibility

The fungibility⁵ of the shared resources means being able to quantify them in a way that allows comparing apples to apples. Dellingr addresses the sharing primarily of HPC resources, which are traditionally mostly CPU-intensive, however the goal of the model is to be able to address sharing of different layers of storage (online, nearline, offline), special types of computers (e.g. GPUs), application experts and more. Organizational issues in differences are covered also in the DO3 report [2] from the Phase 1 of the Dellingr project.

Considering the standard computing nodes from each of the national providers, these may be interchanged between HPC centres with little effort as the hardware (power supply, connectors, racks etc) is standardized. The issues of interchangeability of resources is apparent when considering everything else after the hardware: operating system version; versions of libraries; installed software, associated support of the above, infrastructure certifications and structure of financing that went into the capital expenditures.

Given the issues seen in trying to determine a consistent set of benchmarks (software not installed or out of date, compiler differences etc) and licensing issues of commercial software in the pilot, the shared resources cannot be regarded as fungible in the general case.

The shared resources may be considered fungible in the simple case of a computing project that uses software that is either written by the applicant or an open-source or a statically compiled executable.

As the resources generally are not fungible, then implicitly they have differing values and some sort of exchange rate is required.

6.2 Exchange rates

Several methods for exchange rates of resources have been considered. One of the main goals was to address the possibilities of “trading” different types of resources to be able to build an transparent and balanced framework of resource sharing.

Transparent means that the rules of sharing should be open and agreed upon by existing and new stakeholders. Balanced means that it should be identifying “freeloaders” and highlighting “sponsors” as well as providing means for a country to balance out the cross-border usage.

The exact methods for defining exchange rates for the resources will be worked on during the Phase 2 of the Dellingr project, below we provide three examples with initial models we have considered. Given the fact that in many countries such exchange rate models are already in place (e.g. Billing Units in CSC.fi), we are looking at three possible scenarios:

⁵One kilogram of pure gold is equivalent to any other kilogram of pure gold, whether in the form of coins, ingots, or in other states, gold is fungible.

1. Taking a model from one of the countries, expanding it to a cross-border collaboration;
2. Creating a "common denominator" model that would not require any modifications in each participating country;
3. Taking a hybrid approach by devising a new exchange rate mechanism based on most fitting properties from participating countries.

6.2.1 Example of using CPU-based exchange rate

One possible exchange rate is the direct exchange of contributed core-hours over some defined periods of time. At the end of a time period, the exchanged core-hours are accounted and the balance carried over to the next period. In this fashion a “bank” of core-hours is maintained and, over time, the credits/debits should balance to zero. In the case of the Dellingr pilot, the quantity of core-hours delivered can be considered. Each country contributed core-hours to the Dellingr pilot call as shown in Table 1. The “value” of the core-hours contributed to the pilot call by each national provider is

HPC Provider	core-hours (M)	Weight 1	Weight 2
DK (SDU)	1.2	0.214	0.0245
EST (ETAIS)	1.0*	0.769	0.0336
FI (CSC)	0.75*	0.136	0.0173
IS (HI)	0.1	0.333	0.0200
SE (SNIC/LUNARC)	0.3	0.031	0.0061
NO	n/a	n/a	n/a

Table 1: Approximate core-hours (standard nodes) contributed to Dellingr pilot call. In some cases the number of national billing-units is used to approximate to core-hours. * indicates GPU as well as CPU.

impossible to calculate consistently using pricing. Therefore some other methods to estimate the core-hour values must be employed. One simple method is to weight the core-hours:

1. **By national population:** a simple inverse weight by country population [3].
2. **By GDP per capita:** a simple inverse weight by GDP per capita [3]

As can be seen in Table 1, the number of contributed core-hours varies widely between national providers.

Weighting by population seems like a reasonable proposition ⁶ as it would account for a country's ability to support national computing e-infrastructure. This weighting, as shown in column "Weight 1" in Table 1, is not appropriate as it does not take into account the differing national academic computing models. For example: Sweden has many more independent universities and institutes that comprise the SNIC computing effort making a large contribution more complex; whereas Finland has concentrated the majority of resources at CSC that can more easily assign a large amount of resources. Smaller countries that have centralized their academic computing will perform very well with this weighting.

Weighting by GDP per capita is another simple option, as shown in column "Weight 2" in Table 1, as this attempts to account for a the overall level of wealth of each country. Again, countries that have a more centralized academic computing perform well under this weighting.

An exchange rate based on CPU only has a drawback of ignoring important and potential expensive aspects of service delivery, in particular popularity, utilization and user support level.

6.2.2 Example of using academic pricing-based exchange rate

Another exchange rate could be based on the cost of usage that each national provider charges to academic users. Each cost would need to be weighted by the specifications and common benchmark (see Section 7) of the provided resource e.g. CPU/GPU type, RAM and network. The cost of CPU/GPU usage are available from some countries (EE, DK, FI [4]). These costs, for a standard node (as opposed to a large-RAM or GPU node), are remarkably similar within 5% (modulo exchange rate fluctuations). Iceland has no cost associated for academic usage of computing resources, once an application is evaluated by a committee it receives the resources without even an "internal accounting" cost attached. In Sweden, the costs for computing resources are not standardized across SNIC [5] but are calculated by each institute that runs a HPC centre: these prices are not publicly available. In Estonia each academic resource provider can determine its own academic and commercial pricing, which must be publicly shared. For internal users academic pricing is typically used for show-back or chargeback. Academic pricing is typically subsidized pricing. Within Estonia for nationally funded resources a certain cross-usage percentage must be available at no cost. For external collaborations resource providers are free to decide on their own.

A problem with the academic pricing model is that the prices may not reflect the reality of running the resources i.e. subsidies may be hidden within the prices. Accounting for resources using units of currency also runs the risk of attracting the attention of VAT issues, which could cause additional overhead in accounting for the participating stakeholders.

⁶e.g. A contribution of anything from the USA can be thought to be 10 times less "valuable" than the same quantity from Canada. Given that the countries are similar in many ways apart from a factor of 10 in population and economy.

6.2.3 Example of using popularity-based exchange rate

A proposal for an exchange rate between the contributed resources is based on the “popularity” of resources within the contributed pool. From the perspective of a user, they want to obtain the most suitable resources in order to complete their computing project in the shortest time. The users consult a list of relevant benchmarks (see Section 7) in order to apply to the most suitable shared resource for their computing project. Given this model, the “popularity” of resources will become apparent. The most “popular” resources (i.e. those that proportionally have the most applications) will be weighted against those that are less so. Over time, national providers that provide resources that are used more heavily will build up a credit against those that provide lesser-used resources.

A framework or service needs to be in place in order to calculate the exchange rate using this data.

7 Benchmarking the Pilot Resources

In order to understand the capabilities of the different computing resources contributed to the Dellingr pilot, the resources are benchmarked.

Several benchmark methods were used, outcomes are described below.

7.1 LINPACK benchmark

One obvious idea is to benchmark with the High Performance LINPACK [6] (LINPACK), but this was deemed to be inadequate for several reasons:

- LINPACK does not reflect the problem that the vast majority of users want to solve;
- The LINPACK benchmark is generally highly optimized and does not reflect the reality of the machine speed that the users see. Running LINPACK with a minimal parameter set penalizes specialized resources such as high-RAM nodes.
- Getting LINPACK numbers for GPU equipped nodes is problematic.

A LINPACK benchmark can also be deduced from the theoretical performance of the nodes i.e clock speed and number of operations per cycle. This gives a few percent accuracy to a benchmark but loses the important effect of the networking in a HPC installation.

7.2 PRACE benchmarks

Application specific benchmarking is an alternative to benchmarking with LINPACK. The concept is to use a suite of commonly used software packages that are used by the users of the resources.

The PRACE [7] project have standardized a set of software packages to be used as benchmarks. The Unified European Application Benchmark Suite [8] is a set of 12 application codes that form a single suite. This suite provides a set of scalable, currently relevant and publicly available codes and datasets that are maintained into the future. The datasets are defined for running on PRACE Tier-0 or Tier-1 sized systems, in the Dellingr pilot case the smaller dataset is adequate.

For the Dellingr pilot resources, the benchmarks that are chosen are:

- GROMACS: A package to perform molecular dynamics, simulating the Newtonian equations of motion for systems with hundreds to millions of particles.
- CP2K: A program to perform atomistic and molecular simulations of solid state, liquid, molecular and biological systems.

This subset of the of the PRACE benchmarking suite was chosen due to these programs being already available at some of the HPC centres participating in the Dellingr pilot as well as reflecting a portion of current usage at these centres. Furthermore the selection of compiler toolchain, MPI suite and other libraries used in building and running these benchmarks was deliberately kept unrestricted to best represent the environment at each HPC centre. In the case of resource exchange model 4 “Continuous exchange of computing projects between countries” in Section 4, it can be seen to be advantageous for a HPC centre to run and advertise as complete a set of benchmarks as possible to further highlight each centres strengths, thus this subset of benchmarks used by the Dellingr project might increase with time. To facilitate that these benchmarks are rerun as centres acquire new hardware or as further centres join the project, all benchmarks where run within the Juelich Benchmarking Environment [9] for portability and ease of use. Table 2 gives the benchmark results from the participating HPC centres.

HPC Provider	GROMACS	CP2K
EST (ETAIS)	27.606	not run
DK		
FI(CSC)	14.658	1353.137
IS (HI)	13.059	not run
SE (SNIC/LUNARC)	22.771	not run
NO	not run	not run

Table 2: Walltime in seconds, smaller is better.

HPC Provider	nodes	core/ node	CPU type	Memory	Inter- connect	Compiler toolchain
EST (ETAIS)	4	20	Intel Xeon E5-2660v2 2.20GHz	64GB DDR3	Infiniband 4x QDR	Intel 2015.0 GCC 5.2.0
DK						
FI (CSC)	4	24	Intel Haswell E5-2690v3 2.6GHz	128 GB DDR4	Infiniband FDR	Intel 2016.0 GCC 4.9.3
IS (HI)	4	32	Intel Xeon Gold 6130 2.1GHz	192 GB DDR4	Omnipath x8	Intel 2017.2 GCC 5.4.0
SE (SNIC/LUNARC)	4	20	Intel Haswell E5-2650v3 2.3GHz	64 GB DDR4	Infiniband FDR	Intel 2016.3
NO						

Table 3: Benchmarking setup at the participating HPC centres.

8 Cross-border resource marketplace

To improve cross-border resource requesting and managing, as well as to perform easier analysis of usage, and sharing metrics, the Dellingr project conclude that a technical platform is needed. This platform, referenced as self-service portal hereafter, should be aimed at end-users (researchers), service providers and funders (or national coordinators) for simplifying and formalizing resource exchange mechanism.

The self-service portal is aimed at fitting user requests with national access policies identified in DO2 [10], in particular it should provide strong enough links with digital identities of the users to allow automated processing of requests. Details of AAI requirements are subject for the future deliverable.

The planned functionality for the portal from the point of view of the end-user, should:

- Be able to see list of shared pool of resources along with resource meta-data;
- Be able to see the current state and the availability of resources;
- Be able to request new resources of different types from the shared pool;
- Be able to see historical requests and their outcomes;
- Be able to see actual consumption of resources;

- Be able to link consumption of resources with scientific outcomes;
- Be able to manage people that have access to resources in a safe manner.

The planned functionality for the portal from the point of view of the service provider, should:

- Be able to see current and historical users that have received access via cross-border sharing platform;
- Be able to update usage details of the current allocations;
- Be able to see the scientific results of the calculations performed on service provider's infrastructure.

The planned functionality for the portal from the point of view of the federation broker (e.g. NeIC), should:

- Be able to collect metrics identified in subsection 3.1;
- Be able to see aggregated statistics of cross-usage across countries;
- Be able to see live dashboards with resource allocations and consumptions across countries;
- Be able to potentially drive financial decision based on the metrics from the system.

A technical platform satisfying the needs identified below should be open and extensible to support further evolution of the cross-sharing processes.

9 Summary

The benefits of sharing HPC resources have been outlined and a mechanism to exchange resources is proposed. This mechanism must respect the procedures of the participating countries and needs an acceptable general user agreement. The Dellingr pilot project has indeed demonstrated that resources can be shared across borders but also highlights the difficulties in establishing exchange rates between resources. Rather than relying on CPU or monetary-based exchange rates, an exchange rate based on resource popularity is proposed. This popularity-based exchange rate does not apply to a proposed second pilot nor to the future continuous exchange of resources. The capabilities of the shared resources are measured through a suite of standard benchmarks that try to reflect the user requirements. A technical framework that will encapsulate the above points is proposed.

References

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